

Comparing Water Management Trends, Pressures, and Blue City Index of Shanghai and Ulaanbaatar Using the City Blueprint Approach

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Abstract

Developing cities face growing water challenges that require proactive and adaptive management. Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia experiences severe seasonal water scarcity, limited wastewater treatment, and aging infrastructure, while Shanghai, China as a rapidly urbanizing megacity, faces flooding, pollution, and complex water governance issues. Extreme weather events, including flash floods and prolonged droughts, together with urbanization and climate change, exacerbate these pressures, threatening public health, economic development, and environmental sustainability. This study applies the City Blueprint Approach (CBA) to evaluate and compare water resources management in Ulaanbaatar and Shanghai. Results indicate that the environmental category of the Trends and Pressures Framework (TPF), Shanghai scored 7.3, whereas Ulaanbaatar scored 3.8. Similarly, within the solid waste treatment category of the City Blueprint Framework (CBF), Shanghai achieved a score of 9.3 compared with Ulaanbaatar's 1.1, representing the largest disparity observed in the assessment. These differences are closely associated with variations in technological development and the distinct environmental conditions of the two cities. The study concludes that adaptive, integrated, and context-specific water management frameworks can improve urban resilience and sustainability, offering lessons for other developing and rapidly urbanizing cities facing similar water challenges. This research places greater emphasis on the BCI results and conducts the comparative analysis primarily based on these outcomes. Shanghai is classified as a water-efficient city (BCI = 5.7), supported by extensive wastewater treatment, expanding tertiary treatment, and more advanced waste management, while Ulaanbaatar is categorized as a wasteful city (BCI = 2.5), reflecting aging infrastructure, inadequate wastewater treatment, and limited climate adaptation capacity.

Keywords: *City blueprint index, trend and pressures, urban water management, wastewater and solid waste management, sustainable development.*

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Introduction

Global climate change has emerged as one of the most pressing global challenges facing humanity in recent decades. Globally, the effects of climate change are becoming increasingly evident through rising

global temperatures, shifting precipitation patterns, and increasingly severe water-related disasters ((WMO), 2025).

As of 2025, 45% of the world's 8.2 billion people live in urban areas, a share that has doubled since 1950. Projections indicate that two thirds of global population growth through 2050 will occur in cities (Nations, 2025). According to the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), the global mean temperature has already increased by 1.5°C compared to pre-industrial levels, and globally, the effects of climate change are becoming increasingly evident through rising global temperatures, shifting precipitation patterns, and increasingly severe water-related disasters. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) predicts that in the years to come, these extreme weather events will only get more intense and less predictable((WMO), 2024; Dodman et al., 2022).

Against the backdrop of rapid urban population growth and escalating climate change risks, urban areas are increasingly subject to intense environmental pressures that constrain sustainable development. These pressures include water stress and scarcity, heightened flood risk, water pollution, groundwater depletion, expanding demands for wastewater and solid waste treatment, urban heat island effects, adverse public health impacts, land subsidence, biodiversity loss, rising energy consumption, water insecurity, and ageing water supply and sanitation infrastructure (Chang et al., 2020). The climate change affects water supply through several key factors. Rising temperatures increase evaporation and reduce snowpack, especially in arid and semi-arid regions. Changes in precipitation patterns cause more frequent droughts and floods worldwide. Sea level rise leads to saltwater intrusion into fresh-water sources in coastal cities. Moreover, the growing frequency of extreme weather events disrupts water supply infrastructure in vulnerable areas (Borah, 2025). Collectively, these challenges underscore the urgent need to align urban development pathways with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Water lies at the core of the SDGs and is directly and indirectly linked to many of the other goals. The CBA provides a structured tool that guides cities to-ward sustainable water management by integrating water, waste, and climate adaptation policies with broader urban systems. This methodology supports stakeholders in developing long-term strategies and operational plans, while also enabling city-to-city learning (C2C) (Dieperink, Koop, Witjes, Van Leeuwen, & Driessen, 2023).

The contrast between Shanghai and Ulaanbaatar illustrates the diversity of conditions under which cities must pursue sustainable water management. Shanghai is a highly dense metropolis with stable water sources and technologically advanced infrastructure, while Ulaanbaatar operates in a cold climate, depends almost entirely on groundwater, and maintains relatively vulnerable infrastructure systems (Fan et al., 2024; Munkhsuld, Ochir, Koop, van Leeuwen, & Batbold, 2020).

Despite these contrasts, both cities experience common pressures, including increasing water demand, rising wastewater loads, and the urgent need to modernize aging infrastructure. Conducting a comparative assessment therefore provides important insights: it helps identify best practices that are applicable regardless of city size or development stage and reveals how successful approaches in megacities can be contextually adapted rather than simply replicated. Furthermore, the latest evaluations of urban water management applying the CBA were carried out in 2020, respectively (Chang et al., 2020; Munkhsuld et al., 2020). However, the CBA methodology was revised in 2021 to incorporate updated indicators and improved evaluation criteria. This study aims to reassess Shanghai and Ulaanbaatar using the revised City Blueprint indicators, compare category-level performance and key indicator drivers, and propose city-specific priority interventions based on the BCI decomposition.

Materials and Methods

The study required a variety of data, which were obtained from reliable sources such as national and local statistical databases, international and national reports, academic articles, journals, official websites, and were used for subsequent calculations and analysis. For information not publicly accessible or unavailable

online, additional data were acquired through formal requests submitted to the relevant institutions. Also, to ensure comparability between the two cities, data sources were standardized across both national and city levels.

The main research methodology is the CBA, and the analysis was carried out using Microsoft Excel software as described in the E-Brochure. City Blueprint is an easy-to-use assessment tool that enables the rapid identification of strengths and weaknesses in the urban water cycle, supports strategic decision-making, and provides a foundation for long-term sustainable planning (S. H. A. Koop & van Leeuwen, 2015; S. H. A. L. Koop, C.J. van, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c).

Study Area

This study focuses on two contrasting cities: Shanghai, China, and Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, which were selected to represent distinct stages of urban development, governance systems, and environmental contexts in East and Central Asia.

Figure 1. Map of the Study Areas, Shanghai (Orange) and Ulaanbaatar (Blue)
Source: World Bank

Shanghai is one of China's largest and most economically advanced cities, located on the eastern coast at the mouth of the Yangtze River. It serves as a global financial, commercial, and logistics hub, with a highly developed urban infrastructure and strong integration into international markets. The city has experienced rapid urbanization over the past decades, accompanied by significant investments in transportation networks, water and wastewater systems, environmental management, and smart city technologies (Liu, 2007; Zhu & Chang, 2020).

Ulaanbaatar, the capital of Mongolia, is located in a high-altitude in-land basin along the Tuul River, characterized by a cold, semi-arid continental climate and a landlocked geographic context (ADB, 2020). The city concentrates nearly half of the national population and serves as the country's dominant political, economic, and cultural center. Urban growth has been driven primarily by rural–urban migration,

resulting in rapid spatial expansion, particularly in low-density peri-urban ger districts. Infrastructure development has lagged behind population growth, placing pressure on water supply, sanitation, housing, and transportation systems. Ulaanbaatar relies predominantly on groundwater aquifers for municipal water supply, making water resource management and contamination control critical policy issues (ADB, 2020; "Master plan 2040 ", 2021).

Shanghai's humid subtropical climate and its diversified, the Huangpu River and the Yangtze River sourced surface-water system (Finlayson et al., 2013) stand in sharp contrast to Ulaanbaatar's extreme continental climate, deep seasonal freezing, and near-total reliance on the Tuul River's alluvial aquifers, yielding fundamentally different baseline water-risk profiles. Yet the cities also share features, rapid urban population growth, rising demand, and a seasonal concentration of precipitation (Mongolia's rainy season and Shanghai's summer monsoon months) that make them comparable.

CBA

The CBA is a comprehensive methodology designed to assess and enhance urban water management and sustainability. This approach has been primarily developed and studied by KWR Water Research Institute in Netherlands, and to date, it has been applied in studies of 125 cities worldwide. As illustrated in Figure 2, the CBA consists of three complementary frameworks (Dieperink et al., 2023; Huyghe, Hernández-Pacheco Algaba, van Leeuwen, Koop, & Eisenreich, 2021; S. H. A. Koop et al., 2017; S. H. A. Koop & van Leeuwen, 2015; Leeuwen, 2021; Munkhsuld et al., 2020).

Figure 2. Framework of the City Blueprint Approach. TPF and CBF, which are Explained in This Paper, are in the Blue Box

Source: KWR Water Research Institute

- 1) Trends and Pressures Framework (TPF): This framework evaluates the social, environmental, financial, and governmental challenges that cities face. It uses 24 indicators to identify pressures such as water scarcity, flood risk, water quality, air quality, and urbanization rates (S. H. A. L. Koop, C.J. van, 2021b).
- 2) City Blueprint Framework (CBF): The CBF assesses the performance of urban water management using 24 indicators across 7 categories: Basic water services, Water quality, Wastewater treatment, Water infrastructure, Solid waste, Climate adaptation, and Plans and actions. The Blue City Index (BCI) is derived from these indicators, providing a quantitative measure of a city's water management performance (S. H. A. L. Koop, C.J. van, 2021a).

3) Water Governance Capacity Framework (GCF): The GCF evaluates governance conditions that influence urban water management, including stakeholder cooperation, implementing capacity, and public awareness (S. H. A. L. Koop, C.J. van, 2021c).

Using the CBA, two separate studies covering Shanghai and Ulaanbaatar had previously been conducted in 2020 (Chang et al., 2020; Munkhsuld et al., 2020). However, in 2021, several revisions were introduced to this methodology.

Specifically, within the first sub-framework, the scoring ranges of indicators such as burden of disease and urban drainage flood were revised; the political instability indicator was replaced by female participation; and new World Bank indicators were added. In contrast, within the second sub-framework, the drinking water consumption indicator was removed (S. H. A. L. Koop, C.J. van, 2021a, 2021b).

In addition, for Ulaanbaatar, this study updated and reanalyzed several indicators that had previously been calculated using national level data, by incorporating city level datasets to improve the accuracy and relevance of the assessment.

Trends and Pressures Framework

TPF aims to comprehensively assess the major challenges faced by cities. While studies conducted prior to 2021 evaluated these challenges within three main categories, the present study applies an updated version of the framework that assesses four categories: social pressures, environmental pressures, financial pressures, and governance indicators of the World Bank. The framework consists of 19 main indicators and 24 sub-indicators, including 6 newly added World Bank governance indicators (S. H. A. L. Koop, C.J. van, 2021b). The TPF indicators are scored on a scale between 0 (no concern) to 10 (great concern).

Table 1. TPF Indicators

Category	Indicators		Data source	Data used	
I. Social	1	Urbanization rate	CIA ¹	CIA	
	2	Burden of disease	WHO ²	WHO	
	3	Education rate	World Bank	World Bank	
	4	Female participation			
II. Environmental	Flood risk	5	Urban drainage flood	EEA ³ , Various data sources	SMBS ⁴ , Empirical studies
		6	River peak discharges		Local sources, Empirical studies
		7	Sea level rise		WWF ⁵ , Empirical studies
		8	Land subsidence		
	Water scarcity	9	Freshwater scarcity	FAO ⁶	World Bank
		10	Groundwater scarcity	IGRAC ⁷	ADB ⁸
		11	Sea water intrusion (and/or salinization)	EEA, Joint Research Centre: European soil portal	Article
	Water quality	12	Biodiversity	EEA, Yale ⁹	Yale, World Bank
	Heat risk	13	Heat island	Europe Arcgis, EEA	World Bank
	Air Quality PM2.5/10	14	PM2.5/10	WHO, World Bank	Local sources

III. Financial	15	Economic pressure	IMF ¹⁰	Local sources
	16	Unemployment rate	World Bank	
	17	Poverty rate		
	18	Investment freedom	The Heritage Foundation	The Heritage Foundation
IV. Governance	19	Voice and accountability	World Bank	World Bank
	20	Political Stability		
	21	Government effectiveness		
	22	Regulatory quality		
	23	Rule of law		
	24	Control of corruption		

Note: ¹Central Intelligence Agency, ²World Health Organization, ³European Environmental Agency, ⁴Shanghai Municipal Bureau of Statistics, ⁵World Wildlife Fund, ⁶Food and Agriculture Organization, ⁷International Groundwater Resources Assessment Centre, ⁸Asian Development Bank, ⁹Yale university: Environmental Performance Index, ¹⁰International Monetary Fund

Although the methodology originally proposed calculating several indicators at the national level using data from the World Bank and other international organizations, this study adopts city level data wherever available, as city level analysis provides greater explanatory power for interpreting city water performance. Accordingly, indicators were calculated using city level statistics when such data were accessible; otherwise, nationally reported data were used as proxies for comparative purposes. For example, indicators such as poverty rate, air quality, and unemployment are regularly compiled by municipal statistical authorities in accordance with internationally standardized methodologies and subsequently disseminated through international organizations, ensuring both methodological consistency and data reliability.

City Blueprint Framework

In 2019, when governance indicators were added into the TPF, a minor revision was also made to the CBF. The drinking water consumption indicator was removed, and the assessment currently comprises 24 indicators across 7 categories (S. H. A. L. Koop, C.J. van, 2021a). The CBF indicators are scored on a scale between 0 (poor performance) to 10 (excellent performance).

Table 2. CBF Indicators

Category	Indicators	Data source	Data used
I. Basic water services	1 Access to drinking water	WHO/UNICEF, Various data sources	WSA ² , NBSC ³
	2 Access to sanitation	OECD ¹ , UN, FAO, Eurostat	NSO ⁴ , NBSC
	3 Drinking water quality	Various data sources	WSA, SWA ⁵
II. Water quality	4 Secondary WWT	OECD, IWA ⁶ Water Wiki	NSO, SWA
	5 Tertiary WWT		WSA, Local source
	6 Groundwater quality	EEA ⁷ , Various data sources	WSA, SWA
III. Wastewater treatment	7 Nutrient recovery	OECD	WSA, Local source
	8 Energy recovery	OECD, Local source	
	9 Sewage sludge recycling		
	10 Energy efficiency WWT	Local source	WSA, MED ⁸ , Local source
IV. Infrastructure	11 Stormwater separation	Local source	AGHS ¹⁰ , WSA, SDF ¹¹
	12 Average age sewer		WSA, Article
	13 Water system leakages	Green City Index, Local source	WSA, Green city index
	14 Operating costs recovery (ratio)	IBNET ⁹ , Local source	WSA, Local source

V. Solid waste treatment	15	Solid waste collected	OECD, Waste Atlas, WB, Local source	NSO, NBSC
	16	Solid waste recycled		NSO, SWA
	17	Solid waste energy recovery		MECC ¹² , Article
VI. Climate adaptation	18	Green space	EAA, Satellite maps google	Article, NBSC
	19	Climate adaptation	Various data sources	Mongol Bank, Local sources
	20	Climate robust buildings		Local sources
VII. Plans and actions	21	Management and action plans	Various data sources	Local sources, Empirical studies
	22	Water efficiency measures		
	23	Drinking water consumption	Local source	NSO, NBSC
	24	Attractiveness	Various data sources	Local sources, Empirical studies

Note: ¹Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, ²Water and Sewerage Authority of Ulaanbaatar, ³National Bureau of Statistics of China, ⁴National Statistics Office of Mongolia, ⁵Shanghai water authority, ⁶International Water Association, ⁷European Environment Agency, ⁸Ministry of Economy and Development of Mongolia, ⁹International benchmarking network for water and sanitation utilities, ¹⁰Agency for Geodesy and Hydraulic Structures of Mongolia, ¹¹Shanghai Drainage Facilities, ¹²Ministry of Environment and Climate Change of Mongolia

A key characteristic of this framework is that the Blue City Index (BCI) is calculated using the geometric mean of all indicators. Scores are standardized on a scale from 0 to 10, based on which cities are classified into 5 performance categories (S. H. A. L. Koop, C.J. van, 2021a).

For the data analysis in this framework, most of the data were obtained from national and city statistical offices as well as agencies responsible for water management. Although the methodology prescribed using national level data from some international organizations such as the Asian Development Bank and the World Bank, city level data were openly available, so the assessment was conducted at the city level. For Ulaanbaatar, detailed information was obtained from specialists in the Water and Sewerage Authority, the Ulaanbaatar City Statistics Office, the Ministry of Environment and Climate Change, and other relevant organizations. Similarly, for Shanghai, data were sourced from the National Bureau of Statistics of China, Shanghai statistical yearbook, statistical publications, and other academic articles.

Table 3. Categorization of BCI

BCI	0 – 2	2 – 4	4 – 6	6 – 8	8 – 10
City Classification	Cities lacking basic water services	Wasteful cities	Water efficient cities	Resource efficient and adaptive cities	Water wise cities

Based on this index, Ulaanbaatar received a score of 2.3, wasteful city, while Shanghai scored 5.2, classifying it as a resource efficient and adaptive city (Chang et al., 2020; Munkhsuld et al., 2020) in 2020. The BCI was calculated using the geometric mean of the 24 CBF indicators, and because some indicators were assigned a value of zero, the following formula was applied to derive the final score. $BCI = \sqrt[j]{(F_1 + 1)(F_2 + 1)(F_3 + 1) \dots (F_j + 1)} - 1$, where F_j is jth CBF indicator. High BCI scores represent good performance on Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM).

Results

TPF assessment

The TPF assessment shows that Shanghai achieved a higher overall performance than Ulaanbaatar across the 24 indicators. Ulaanbaatar performed relatively better in the social and financial categories, whereas Shanghai substantially outperformed Ulaanbaatar in environmental indicators. This disparity reflects Ulaanbaatar's geographic and hydro-environmental constraints, including reliance on groundwater and limited emphasis on biodiversity and climate related pressures, while Shanghai faces distinct coastal challenges such as freshwater scarcity, groundwater scarcity, and seawater intrusion. Governance scores were broadly comparable; however, given Shanghai's advanced institutional capacity, national level indicators may underestimate its actual governance performance.

Across the 24 indicators grouped into four categories, Shanghai achieved an average score of 5.4, while Ulaanbaatar scored 4.3. When comparing the average values by category, Ulaanbaatar outperformed Shanghai in social indicators by 0.4 points and in financial indicators by 1.5 points, suggesting that greater emphasis may be required on these dimensions.

Table 4. The Result of TPF

Category	Indicators	Score	
		Ulaanbaatar	Shanghai
I. Social	1 Urbanization rate	3.0	3.8
	2 Burden of disease	4.0	3.0
	3 Education rate	3.8	3.5
	4 Female participation	4.2	3.1
II. Environmental	5 Urban drainage flood	10.0	10.0
	6 River peak discharges	2.5	5
	7 Sea level rise	0.0	10.0
	8 Land subsidence	0.0	7.5
	9 Freshwater scarcity	0.0	5.0
	10 Groundwater scarcity	0.0	5.0
	11 Sea water intrusion	0.0	7.5
	12 Biodiversity	3.6	9.1
	13 Heat island	6.4	8.2
	14 PM2.5/10	6.4	3.5
III. Financial	15 Economic pressure	8.8	6.7
	16 Unemployment rate	2.5	0.7
	17 Poverty rate	3.5	0.0
	18 Investment freedom	3.7	5.1
IV. Governance	19 Voice and accountability	4.5	8.0
	20 Political Stability	3.8	6.0
	21 Government effectiveness	5.9	3.6
	22 Regulatory quality	5.4	5.7
	23 Rule of law	5.4	5.1
	24 Control of corruption	6.0	5.0

Ulaanbaatar shows particularly great concern for several indicators. The Urban drainage flood and Economic pressure indicators received scores of 10.0 and 8.8, respectively, indicating issues that require urgent attention. This is followed by Heat island (6.4) and PM2.5/10 (6.0), which also represent notable pressures that warrant policy focus and mitigation measures. For Shanghai, the assessment indicates that Urban drainage flood, Sea level rise, Biodiversity, Heat island, and Voice and accountability are key areas requiring significant attention. In particular, the Urban drainage flood indicator is calculated by considering the risk of flooding due to intensive rainfall expressed as the share of urban soil that is sealed, excluding green spaces from the total city area. Both cities have high population density and extensive

built-up areas; however, the share of green space differs substantially, accounting for only 1.8% in Ulaanbaatar (Enkhbold & Matsui, 2022) compared with 27% in Shanghai (Statistics, 2025). This contrast partly explains differences in urban flood vulnerability between the two cities.

Figure 3. The Result of TPF by Indicators

Sea level rise in Shanghai is being intensified by land subsidence across the Yangtze River Delta. Current estimates indicate subsidence levels of approximately 2.0–2.6 m, largely associated with increasing groundwater extraction driven by rapid population growth and urban expansion. In addition, projections suggest that sea levels may rise by about 50–70 cm by 2050, which could significantly increase the risk of coastal inundation. Model simulations further indicate that a 0.3 m rise in sea level could result in the inundation of approximately 54,500 km² in the delta region. Moreover, flooding has emerged as a major climate-related risk, as the frequency of extreme rainfall events has increased over the past decade and is expected to continue rising under future climate change scenarios. These factors collectively highlight the high vulnerability of Shanghai to climate change impacts (International, 2009). Therefore, Shanghai received the maximum score of 10 for both the Urban drainage flood and Sea level rise indicators.

In contrast, Ulaanbaatar scored 3.5 points lower than Shanghai on environmental indicators. This lower performance can be explained by the city’s geographical and natural conditions: it is located at an altitude of approximately 1,350 meters (4,429 feet) above sea level, landlocked, relies primarily on groundwater as a source of drinking water, and places relatively less emphasis on issues such as the urban heat island effect and biodiversity ("Master plan 2040 ", 2021; Mongolia, 2023). Consequently, its environmental evaluation appears weaker in comparison with Shanghai. By contrast, Shanghai, situated at the mouth of the Yangtze River, is regularly affected by saltwater intrusion in the Yangtze, Qiantang, and Pearl River estuaries, particularly between October and March, and recent academic studies have identified freshwater scarcity, groundwater stress, and seawater intrusion as critical challenges that increasingly demand policy and management attention in the city (Tao et al., 2024).

For World Bank governance indicators, national level assessments show that Ulaanbaatar’s average score is 0.4 points lower than that of Shanghai. In Mongolia, nearly half of the national population resides in Ulaanbaatar, which means the city may be reasonably representative of national conditions. However, in China, governance performance varies considerably across provinces and cities. Therefore, it is questionable whether this score fully reflects Shanghai’s governance performance.

CBF assessment

The CBF results further highlight clear contrasts between the two cities. Table 4 shows that Shanghai outperforms Ulaanbaatar across all categories and is classified as a water-efficient city, characterized by extensive secondary wastewater treatment, increasing tertiary treatment, partial implementation of water efficient technologies, and comparatively advanced solid waste management. In contrast, Ulaanbaatar is classified as a wasteful city (BCI = 2.5), reflecting inadequate wastewater treatment, aging and leaky infrastructure, landfill dependent solid waste disposal, and weak climate adaptation capacity. For both cities, wastewater treatment represents the lowest performing category, underscoring a common structural challenge among Asian cities.

Table 4. The Result of CBF

Category	Indicators	Ulaanbaatar	Shanghai
I. Basic water services	1 Access to drinking water	9.8	10.0
	2 Access to sanitation	5.0	9.8
	3 Drinking water quality	9.6	10.0
II. Water quality	4 Secondary WWT	5.8	9.8
	5 Tertiary WWT	0.0	10.0
	6 Groundwater quality	9.6	10.0
III. Wastewater treatment	7 Nutrient recovery	0.0	0.0
	8 Energy recovery	0.0	0.0
	9 Sewage sludge recycling	0.0	9.8
	10 Energy efficiency WWT	0.0	5.0
IV. Infrastructure	11 Stormwater separation	4.1	9.5
	12 Average age sewer	6.8	3.7
	13 Water system leakages	6.8	0.0
	14 Operating costs recovery (ratio)	4.1	3.7
V. Solid waste treatment	15 Solid waste collected	2.8	10.0
	16 Solid waste recycled	0.7	10.0
	17 Solid waste energy recovery	0.0	8.0
VI. Climate adaptation	18 Green space	0.0	2.7
	19 Climate adaptation	6.0	8.0
	20 Climate robust buildings	6.0	8.0
VII. Plans and actions	21 Management and action plans	6.0	8.0
	22 Water efficiency measures	6.0	8.0
	23 Drinking water consumption	9.8	5.7
	24 Attractiveness	2.0	8.0
BCI		2.5	5.2

Shanghai is classified as a water-efficient city (BCI = 5.7). This classification indicates the implementation of centralized, well established technological solutions to improve water use efficiency and pollution control. Secondary wastewater treatment coverage is high, and the share of tertiary treatment is increasing. Water efficient technologies are partially applied; infrastructure leakages have been

substantially reduced, although overall water consumption remains high. Energy recovery from wastewater treatment is relatively advanced, while nutrient recovery remains limited. Both solid waste recycling and energy recovery are partially implemented. However, such cities often remain vulnerable to climate change due to insufficient adaptation strategies, limited stormwater separation, and low proportions of green surface areas (Mongolia, 2023). Governance capacity and community involvement have nevertheless improved (Dieperink et al., 2023; S. H. A. L. Koop, C.J. van, 2021a; Van Leeuwen & Sjerps, 2015).

Figure 4. The Result of CPF by Indicators

While Ulaanbaatar, with inadequate wastewater treatment, high infrastructure losses, landfill-dependent waste disposal, and weak climate adaptation, falls into the wasteful cities category (BCI = 2.5). This classification indicates that while basic services are largely covered, wastewater treatment remains inadequate. Typically, only primary and a limited share of secondary treatment are applied, leading to large-scale pollution. Water consumption and infrastructure leakage rates are high due to limited environmental awareness and insufficient infrastructure maintenance (Capital, 2022). The Central WWT Plant alone receives approximately 190,000 to 200,000 cubic meters of wastewater per day. The wastewater undergoes mechanical and chemical treatment, followed by ultraviolet disinfection, before being discharged into the Tuul River. Due to the overcapacity of the Central WWT Plant, its treatment efficiency remains below 80%, indicating a significant strain on its ability to purify wastewater effectively (Munkhsuld et al., 2020).

The discharge of chemically polluted industrial wastewater into a facility designed primarily for domestic sewage disrupts biological treatment processes, preventing effluent from consistently meeting regulatory standards (Tsatsral Ts, 2002). Moreover, the treated effluent is not reused but discharged into surface waters; sludge is not recovered for reuse, and tertiary treatment is not applied (Batsaikhan et al., 2021).

By contrast, as of the end of 2024, Shanghai operates 43 urban wastewater treatment plants with a combined treatment capacity of 10.7075 million cubic meters per day (facilities, 2025). Although publicly

available data do not specify which plants apply nutrient or energy recovery technologies, all municipal sewage sludge is managed through terminal disposal based on sludge drying followed by incineration. National planning documents, including the 14th Five-Year Plan, explicitly promote energy efficiency, and energy-saving technologies in wastewater treatment plants, and these policy objectives are reflected in Shanghai's local wastewater and drainage plans. And Shanghai has the sixth lowest water leakage rate in the Asian green city index, at 10%, versus the Index average of 22% (*Asian Green City Index Assessing the environmental performance of Asia's major cities*, 2011).

The category showing the greatest disparity between the two cities is solid waste management. Shanghai is widely regarded as a high-performing city in this sector due to its mandatory waste-sorting policy introduced in 2019 (municipality, 2023), which has significantly increased source-separation efficiency and reduced residual waste through strong enforcement, public participation, and institutional coordination.

In Ulaanbaatar, Category I achieved the highest score, reflecting that most residents are connected to the drinking water network and that water quality is generally satisfactory. Nevertheless, poor performance in wastewater treatment operations and infrastructure, as well as weak climate adaptation measures, contributed to low overall scores. For example, according to the Ulaanbaatar Water Supply and Sewerage Authority, as of 2023 the total length of wastewater pipelines was 298.8 km, and approximately 50% of the main sewer network is 40–60 years old, has exceeded its service life, and is severely deteriorated, with frequent cracks and failures (Ulaanbaatar, 2024).

Discussion

Based on the available sources, data for cities in European Union countries are generally sufficient and relatively easy to access, whereas for Asian countries, city level data are often unavailable from the open sources. In some cases, certain indicators are not calculated at all or are not publicly disclosed, leading to the assignment of 0 values for several indicators, which poses a risk of biasing the results. Therefore, indicators with missing, uncertain, or exclusively national level data require further in-depth investigation and more refined calculation methods to improve the accuracy and reliability of the results.

Although several World Bank indicators were incorporated as part of efforts to improve the methodology, these indicators are measured at the national level and are therefore not fully appropriate for an assessment framework intended for city level analysis. This limitation is particularly evident in the case of China, which comprises a large number of provinces and cities with substantial variation in levels of urbanization, governance, and development. For instance, instead of the newly added investment freedom indicator, the assessment could add indicators such as the proportion of municipal budget expenditures allocated to water environment protection and green development, which would better capture city specific investment priorities and policy commitments.

Conclusion

This study applied the City Blueprint Approach to comparatively assess urban water management in Ulaanbaatar and Shanghai under conditions of rapid urbanization and increasing climate stress. By integrating the Trends and Pressures Framework (TPF), and the City Blueprint Framework (CBF), the analysis provides a holistic evaluation of environmental, social, financial, and governance dimensions of urban water systems, with particular emphasis on the Blue City Index (BCI) outcomes.

The results reveal a clear performance gap between the two cities. Shanghai demonstrates relatively advanced capacity in basic water services, wastewater treatment, solid waste management, and governance, supported by centralized infrastructure, strong policy frameworks, and sustained investment. Nevertheless, the city continues to face structural challenges related to freshwater and groundwater

scarcity, seawater intrusion, and climate vulnerability, indicating that technological advancement alone is insufficient without stronger public engagement and adaptive water governance. In contrast, Ulaanbaatar's low BCI score reflects persistent weaknesses in wastewater treatment, aging infrastructure, landfill-dependent waste management, and limited climate adaptation capacity, despite relatively good access to basic drinking water services. Seasonal water scarcity and heavy reliance on groundwater further exacerbate the city's vulnerability to climate variability.

Shanghai's experience demonstrates that integrated solid waste management, advanced wastewater treatment with water reuse, and climate-adaptive urban drainage can significantly improve urban water sustainability. Ulaanbaatar can adapt these approaches by gradually introducing source-separated waste collection, modular upgrades to wastewater treatment plants, and nature-based solutions for flood and stormwater management. In addition, Shanghai's use of data-driven monitoring and smart water management highlights the importance of evidence-based decision-making. Strengthening governance capacity through inter-agency coordination and stakeholder participation is equally critical. Overall, adapting these integrated and context-specific practices can enhance Ulaanbaatar's urban water resilience and long-term sustainability.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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